

A Content Analysis of Deixis and References in Jakarta Post

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of the research is to examine the deixis and references of various types in the Jakarta Post. The thematic analysis was used to analyze four Jakarta Post article. In this study, the qualitative method was applied. The findings indicated that numerous types of deixis were detected in the Jakarta Post, including person, spatial, time, discourse, and social. Social deixis was a predominant type. Another outcome was a reference. The anaphoric and cataphoric references were discovered in the Jakarta Post, while the anaphoric reference is being predominant. In short, the majority of Jakarta Post authors used social deixis and anaphoric reference to provide comprehensible information in the written text.

KEYWORDS: Articles, Deixis, Jakarta Post, Newspaper, Reference.

INTRODUCTION

Deixis is one of the pragmatic materials which many people should be aware of. Deixis consists of a feature that provides detailed information about the sentence or speech (Yule, 1996). Furthermore, Deixis improves the reader's comprehension because it involves person, times, place, social, and discourse information that provides the text. Deixis can be found in novels, newspapers, poetry, lyrics, speeches, and other works. In addition, deixis is a type of pragmatics which indicates a language. Deixis can be found in both written and oral form. There are various types of deixis, including person, spatial, time, social, and discouse. Person deixis is a type of deixis which represents a person. It is usually used to refer to a personal pronoun. For instance, I, you, we, they, he, she, it, and so on. Spatial deixis is a deixis which indicates the location, for example, restaurant, here, there, go to bed, cinema, and so on. Time or spatial deixis is a deixis which defines when an event occurs. For example, now, today, tomorrow, Sunday, and so on. Social deixis is a deixis which indicates a person's status in society. For instance, your majesty, your highness, and so on. Discourse deixis is a deixis which demonstrates the discouse of the thing, such as here and there.

Furthermore, it is crucial to comprehend references. One of the pragmatics aspects which learners should be familiar with is reference. Reference is defined as a manner in which a speaker or writer employs language forms to assist a listener or reader recognize something. The reference could be a combination of both anaphoric and cataphoric. An anaphoric reference is one in which the subject's information is clear from the start of the sentence. For example, Jessy is the most beautiful girl in this room. She is extremely talented. "She" refers to "Jessy" in this statement. In contrast, a cataphoric reference is one in which the information of the phrase's engaged appears in the following sentence. As an example, Joe goes to market with her. It is because Tiara promises to company him. In this sentence, the word "her" refers to Tiara. It shows that there is a different pattern both anaphoric and cataphoric term.

Many studies examined the many kinds of deixis in novels, poetry, song lyrics, newspapers, teachers' talks, students' talks, drama, and speech. The results of their experiments were practically the same, as several researchers obtained information on person, place, and time deixis (Quinto, 2014; Sari, 2015; Nugarah, 2015; Purba, 2015; Hasanah, 2016; Asy'ari, et. al, 2017; Putri & Budiarsa, 2018; Wibowo & Nailufar, 2019; Rahayu & Kurniawan, 2019; Laia, 2020), while several found other types of deixis, such as discourse and social deixis (Wahyudi, 2014; Widayanti & Yuwono, 2017; Retnowati, et. al, 2018). In addition, additional relevant research evaluated person deixis between two languages and English teachers, with the results demonstrating that English teachers were more likely to use person deixis than other languages (Novianty, et. al, 2018; Mayori, et. al, 2020). In addition, Jumaedah, Saleh & Harton (2020) investigated the effect of deixis used by teacher for students' understanding. Deixis could influence the students understanding about the material given by the teacher. Therefore, the teacher must optimize using dexis in the teaching and learning process.

Deixis and reference are essential topics to explore since deixes are capable of helping readers comprehend the text better. The purpose of this research is to analyze the deixis and reference various types in the Jakarta Post since the Jakarta Post is a competent daily which publishes both national and international news. The Jakarta Post, which is released every day except Saturday, Sunday, and holidays. This research stands out from previous research since it evaluates additionally to the different types of deixis, but also the reference. The majority of relevant research investigated deixis in novels, songs, and local languages.

METHOD

In order to accomplish the research objectives, The Jakarta Post articles from November, 6th 2023 to November, 10th 2023 were collected. This document is appropriate for this content analysis of qualitative study since the researcher intended to analyze the Jakarta Post's deixis and references. According to Creswell (2014) and Ary, et. al (2010), content analysis is a qualitative research method that works with document analysis. The research instruments were checklist and document. The validation of the instrument was accomplished by triangulation. The data collection procedures were as follows: (1) collecting the Jakarta Post online articles from November, 6th to 10th, (2) using a checklist to see the deixis and references for each article. The researcher collected the data on his own.

In addition, the data was analyzed using theme analysis. According to Heigham & Crocker (2009), thematic analysis is a qualitative data analysis that focuses on identifying, analyzing, and interpreting data. In general, thematic analysis consists of five steps. The first step is getting familiar with the data from the checklist and document. The second step is coding in order to determine the deixis and reference in the Jakarta Post. The third step is creating topic, which implies that the researcher chooses a topic which includes deixis and reference types. The fourth step is labeling by establishing and naming topic. The last step is writing up. It is crucial to complete since it is during this stage that the researcher writes the deixis and reference analysis that were detected and classified in the Jakarta Post.

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Findings

The findings of this study are in line with the research questions or purposes. Those are deixis and references from the Jakarta Post. The findings are gained through the use of a checklist and document analysis.

Types of Deixis

According to the checklist and coding, the findings of deixis are shown in the table below.

Table 1. Types of deixis regarding Jakarta Post

No.	Types of Deixis	Frequency
1.	Person Deixis	138
	1 st	10
	2 nd	6
	3 rd	122
2.	Temporal Deixis	29
3.	Spatial Deixis	100
4.	Social Deixis	219
5.	Discourse Deixis	27

The table 1 reveals that there are 219 words of social deixis, 138 words of person deixis consists of 1st (10), 2nd (6) and 3rd (122) person, 100 spatial deixis, 29 temporal deixis, and 27 discourse deixis identified in the news of Jakarta Post. The majority is social deixis while the minority is discourse deixis. The examples of social deixis are *The Foreign Ministry, Israeli Military, Hamas Foreign Reporters, The Government, Palestinian President, Militias, Foreign Minister Hospital and so on*. The examples of person deixis are *I, My, Me, You, Your, She, He, It, They, We, Them, Their, Its, Him, Our*. Spatial deixis can be seen at *Indonesia Hospital, Gaza, Palestine, Iraq, Air Force Base, Camp, and Baghdad. Monday, Sunday, Saturday, Several Days Ago, Several Years Ago*,

Overnight, Last Week, October 7th, in 2011, and in 2016. Finally, there is discourse deixis. Last deixis examples include That, Where, What, Which, and Whose.

Types of Reference

The following table presents the findings of the reference analysis.

Table 2. Types of reference based on Jakarta Post

No.	Types of Reference	Frequency
1.	Anaphoric	107
2.	Cataphoric	13

According to the table 2., the frequency of anaphoric reference discovered in Jakarta Post is 107 words. In addition, the cataphoric reference is 13. It implies that anaphoric reference dominates than cataphoric reference. These types of references have become more prominent in a written text than oral ones. The example of anaphoric reference found in Jakarta Post is *Since the Hamas attack on Oct. 7, to which Israel immediately responded with a large-scale military operation, the Indonesia Hospital has come into the international media's spotlight (antecedent). It has been covered by prominent TV channels such as CNN, the BBC and Al-Jazeera, as well as global news agencies like Reuters, AFP, AP and Bloomberg (1st article).* Jakarta Post instance of cataphoric reference is *"An Israeli air strike targeted my neighbours' house in Al-Maghazi camp, my house next door partially collapsed," said Mohammed Alaloul, 37, a journalist working for the Turkish Anadolu Agency.*

DISCUSSION

Regarding the purpose of this research, the researcher separated the discussion of the research findings into two parts, those are deixis analysis and reference analysis. Starting off, the deixis analysis in the Jakarta Post investigated numerous types of deixis, including person deixis, time and place deixis, social and discourse deixis. These findings are in line with theory of Yule (1996), which states that there are numerous types of deixis that can be seen in written or oral communication, including person, spatial, temporal, and social. However, there is no explanation for discourse deixis in Yule (1996). In the Jakarta Post articles (November, 6th to November, 10th 2023), the social deixis is dominating. It is possible since the articles utilized by the researcher demonstrates considerable amounts of interaction between one and others based on their position in society in a certain situation. This statement is supported by Levinson (1983), who stated that social deixis is concerned with parts of sentences that consider, determine, or explain by specific information of participants or the social environment in which the speech act occurs. The articles were used in this research basically discuss situations that develop between individuals and governments. The first and third articles discuss the fighting in Gaza. The second article concentrates on Indonesian pioneers in specific events, while the last article examines Trump's concerns about treatment during the New York fraud trial. All of the articles were about people's interactions with how they are perceived in society. It means that what we are discussing impacts the common deixis that we choose to use in communicating. It is in line with Kramsch (1993), he argues the context in which we use language affects the capacity to choose words. Our personal thoughts are influenced by the thoughts of others.

Furthermore, discourse deixis is the least common type of deixis. This is due to the fact that discourse deixis rarely appears in oral or written text. Since discourse is capable of identifying location, most people apply spatial deixis instead of discourse deixis. As the definition of discourse deixis involves the use of a word within an utterance to refer to an aspect of the discourse that includes the word used (Levinson, 1983), it causes the reader or listener to become incapable of identifying with anaphora. Readers and listeners will struggle to figure out which is discourse deixis and which is not. It influences why the writers or speakers rarely use discourse deixis. In addition, Experts have emphasized the difficulties in comprehending discourse deixis due to its complicated character, the requirement for a comprehensive understanding of contextual and pragmatic features, and the particular referent of discourse deixis from the text. Despite its difficulties, understanding discourse deixis is critical for gaining a deeper knowledge of language structure and meaning in communication (Levinson, 1995; Kryk-Kastovsky, 1995; Nurhikmah, 2016).

The findings of this research include not only types of deixis, but also references. The researcher has discovered two categories of references. These are anaphoric and cataphoric references. It is in accordance with theory of Yule (1996) related to anaphoric and

cataphoric references in text or oral form. This research shows that anaphoric reference prevails over cataphoric reference. The total number of references (120 words) divided into anaphoric and cataphoric references demonstrates that anaphoric contains 107 words, whereas cataphoric contains 13 words. Anaphoric references serve an integrated purpose once they appear in a sentence, they should have a clear psychological impact on the reader. The concept relates to outdated material and serves as a marker for the reader's understanding (Sultonov & Zebinso, 2021). Anaphoric references are those that relate to a concept or term that was introduced in previous phrase. It makes the readers or speakers relatively easy to understand.

Moreover, cataphoric tends to be unfamiliar than anaphoric. Cataphoric references are less common than anaphoric references since they point ahead in the text, which means that the speaker or writer will name the referent later rather than straightaway (Awwad, 2017). Furthermore, Virdaus & Rifa'i (2022) claim that certain grammarians refer to a cataphoric a or forward reference as the action or effect of one linguistic unit referencing another. In contrast to an anaphoric, a cataphoric refers to something that has not been mentioned yet. It implies to the reference direction within a sentence or speech, and cataphoric is also known as backward anaphoric. As a result, a cataphoric goes downward, whereas an anaphor attempts ahead. Besides, it is reasonable due to cataphoric references are currently uncommon in text because they are more sophisticated than anaphoric references (Indriyani, 2022; Azarizad & Tohidian, 2012; Panggabean & Khatimah, 2022; Lestari, 2019; Virdaus & Rifa'I, 2022; and Nurhikmah, 2016).

CONCLUSION

Regarding findings and discussion above, all types of deixis are found in Jakarta Post articles (November, 6th to November, 10th 2023). The most frequently arises in these articles is social deixis. It is influenced by the topic of the articles which mostly discuss about people's interaction with government and organization. Additionally, anaphoric reference is the most familiar reference which uses in Jakarta Post articles (November, 6th to November, 10th 2023). It is possible because anaphoric is easier to utilize than cataphoric since anaphoric provides readers or speakers with prior knowledge about something or someone for the first time. In contrast, discourse deixis and cataphoric reference are rarely used by the writers and speakers. It is because most people think that they are too complex one. when they use both of them, it can make others misunderstanding the meaning that they want to convey to others.

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